

ANALISIS GENDER DAN *INTELLECTUAL INTELLIGENCE* TERHADAP KREATIVITAS

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Abstrak

Penelitian bertujuan untuk mengetahui hubungan antara perbedaan gender dan *intellectual intelligence* terhadap kreativitas siswa sekolah dasar. Sampel penelitian berjumlah 60 siswa yang dipilih secara *simple random sampling*. Instrumen yang digunakan yaitu *Coloured Progressive Matrices* dan *Figural Creativity Test* untuk menentukan tingkat *intellectual intelligence* dan kreativitas siswa. Teknik analisis data menggunakan analisis korelasi. Hasil analisis menunjukkan bahwa: kemampuan *intellectual intelligence* berkaitan dengan kemampuan untuk berkreativitas; tidak ditemukan perbedaan gender terhadap kemampuan berkreativitas; dan analisis korelasi berganda terhadap kemampuan *intellectual intelligence* dan perbedaan gender menunjukkan tidak ada hubungan dengan kemampuan kreativitas siswa.

Kata Kunci: kreativitas, *intellectual intelligence*, gender, korelasi.

Abstract

The research aimed to determine the relationship between gender differences and intellectual intelligence on the creativity of elementary school students. The research sample consisted of 60 students who were selected by simple random sampling. The instruments used were Colored Progressive Matrices and Figural Creativity Test to determine the level of intellectual intelligence and creativity of students. The data analysis technique used correlation analysis. The results of the analysis showed that: intellectual intelligence ability was related to the ability to be creative; no gender differences were found on creativity skills; and multiple correlation analysis on intellectual intelligence abilities and gender differences showed no relationship with students' creative abilities.

Keywords: *creativity, intellectual intelligence, gender, correlation.*